

Exploring types and characteristics of cultural products evoking consumers' pleasures

Wu, Tyan Yu * Wu, Jordan Chao-tao **

* *Chang Gung University, the Department of Industrial Design
Tao-Yuan, Taiwan, tnyuwu@mail.cgu.edu.tw*

** *Lombardi Design
New York, USA, jordancwu@yahoo.com*

Abstract: Designing a product with pleasurable value has become a key requirement during the product development stage. Cultural products can enhance the individual difference and further add an extra value in global market. Understanding cultural content can affect a consumer's emotion/ pleasure when observing or using it. Accordingly, to develop a cultural product, designers have to understand types and characteristics of cultural products. This research investigated contemporary cultural products and extracted 14 stimuli for questionnaire survey. The result produced 14 characteristics which can be classified into five types of pleasurable culture products. They are pleasant appearance, playful interaction, cultural content, novelty, and humor/interest. Statistic results show that both male and female have a similar pleasure response towards cultural products. The result also demonstrates that participants showed a higher tendency to purchase a product with pleasure than those without. Furthermore, the result suggests that a product with cultural characteristics may influence users' emotions and that the pleasurable value can affect consumers' decision making when purchasing it.

Key words: *Cultural product, Pleasure, Product types and characteristics.*

1. Introduction

1.1 New perspective of product design

Marzano (1998) commented that "product can be seen as living objects with which people have relationships [1]. Products are objects that can make people happy or angry, proud or ashamed, secure or anxious. Products can empower, infuriate or delight – they have personalities." Jordan (1998) further stated that a product perceived to be pleasurable is used more regularly or purchased more frequently than one without [2]. At this point, consumers demand a product that not only provides a good functionality, ergonomic comforts, and smart interface design, but also has a pleasurable benefit.

Nowadays, a product design with local appeal appears to be more and more important in global market, where products are losing their identity because of the similarity in product function and form. Taking advantage of culture value, local culture is utilized and recognized in product design area, because of its ability to empower

characters into products affectively. Therefore, culture is becoming a value-added element in the enhancement of product identity in the international market and the fulfillment of individual consumers' experience [3-6]. As a result, products embedded with unique culture style allow a consumer to express his or her own taste which becomes a part of personal identity, which evoking a consumer's pleasure feeling.

Interacting with meaning of a product can further evoke users' emotion [7]. In design reality, designers tend to extract cultural elements/ meanings and infuse them into a product in hoping of creating a unique meaning which can further empower consumers' personal identities. Alberto (2000), the president of Alessi, realizes the importance of product emotion, and tend to apply emotions to kitchenware designs in order to create a great success in marketing sale [8]. Similarly, Marzano (1998) agreed that product should provide consumers a wonderful using experience, and evoke their emotion, further fulfill consumers' desire and dreams [1]. Hence, designers at Phillip Design Group utilize product emotion as a strategy to soften technological products. To do so, consumers' life styles and cultural contents were investigated and integrated into a "cool" Hi-tech product which in general results in a success at market.

It is noteworthy that designing a product with local tastes to emphasize its cultural value has become a critical issue in the design process [9,10]. Deeply rooted in Chinese culture, Taiwanese designers eager to use this profuse resource to enrich their designs. For example, in 2007, the "old is new" design project organized by Taiwan's National Palace Museum is a successful collaboration with Italy designer, Stefano Giovannoni. As one of the projects, the pepper and salt shakers displayed an impressive culture image from Chinese Chin's dynasty. The product illustrates a strong cultural roots by using a vivid color element and pattern derived from resplendent images of Chin's emperors and queens. Currently, this find product is selling at Alessi store world wide. Consumers then have a chance to draw closer to this unique Chinese culture in their daily life.

Cultural features are considered to be a unique characteristic that can be embedded into a product both for the enhancement of its identity in the global market and for the enrichment of the individual consumer experience [3,6]. To create a cultural product with pleasurable value, Crossley (2003) further suggested that designers should understand the relationship between product appearance and perception towards product characteristics [11]. Hence, to design a pleasurable product, designers have to understand what cultural elements are affecting consumers' pleasurable response. An exploratory research is needed to identify the types and characteristics of cultural products. The results of this study may provide designers and marketers with a more robust view of pleasure cultural products, when developing a cultural product with pleasure. This is the starting point of this research study.

1.2 Product emotion and culture

Jordan (2000) [12], Marzano (1998) [1], McDonagh-Philp & Lebbon (2000) [13] argued that a product with emotional benefits is very important [14]. Norman (2004) further stated that people are emotional and social creatures, which form social culture slowly [15]. Culture has been described as "the way of life for an entire society" [16,17]. It generally refers to patterns of human activity and the symbolic structures that give such activity significance [6]. As mentioned previous, product that are meant to evoke consumers' positive emotion can add extra value to products, particularly when the product conveys a sense of pleasure [18,19] [2] [20-22].

Crozier (1994) commented that the psychological responses to products are influenced by the product's appearance (including shape, size, and color), and the meaning in their cultural context and the functions they fulfill [23]. Many research results in design, art, and advertising areas also indicate that visual elements such as shape, color, logo, and typeface are not only perceived in terms of their formal or technical properties but also in terms of the symbolic or affective connotations they embody [24]. Overall, we can conclude that consumers' emotions can be derived from both observing of product appearance and the understanding of meaning behind. To understand cultural meaning, it requires having culture experience. As fact, culture can also influence product design [25]. For instance, Alva Aalto (1936) used the shape of Finish lakes as a metaphor to develop 'savoy vase' [26]. Lately, the vase becomes a symbol of Finland and many Finish is proud to have it in their house, because of its symbolic value. In contract, we should investigate if different cultural people also perceive similar emotional value with same condition.

What is cultural product and its emotion? Leong and Clark (2003) described cultural products into three spatial levels: (1) the outer "tangible" level, dealing with color, texture, form, decoration, surface pattern, line quality, and detail, (2) the mid "behavioral" level, dealing with function, operational concerns, usability, and safety, and (3) the inner "intangible" level, containing special content such as stories, emotions, and cultural features[17]. These three spatial levels are also related to traditional culture study in which can be classified into three layers: (1) physical or material culture--including food, garments, and transportation-related objects, (2) social or behavioral culture--including human relationships and social organization, and (3) spiritual or ideal culture--including art and religion. Clearly cultural products are linked with three spatial levels, which can also be referred to as consumer emotional response [15].

Norman (2004) stated that there are three levels of product emotions: visceral design, behavioral design and reflective design [15]. The three levels of emotions can be mapped with three special levels towards cultural design. Visceral design is concerned with the appearance of a cultural object and is aimed to transform its form, textures, and patterns into a new product. The visceral design features become important where appearance matters and lead to the first impressions formed by consumers. The behavioral design level concerns the use, function, performance and usability of a cultural object. Behavioral design features are the key to a product's usefulness. Reflective design concerns the feelings, emotions, and cognition involved in experiencing a cultural object. Being influenced by differences in culture, experience, and education, as well as individual differences, reflective design features are the most sensitive among the three levels to variability.

By adopting Tiger's (1992) four types of pleasure theory [27], Jordan (2000) classified products' pleasures into four categories[12]. The first category contains products with physio-pleasure which involved sensations, for example, touching or seeing something. The second contains products with socio-pleasure. In this category, products can facilitate social interaction such as chatting with friends. For instance, a mobile phone can provide socio-pleasure by using it to chat with friends anywhere, anytime. The third is psycho-pleasure. In terms of products, this relates to the cognitive demands and emotional reactions engendered through experience of using the product. For instance, a good icon interface on computer screen allows users to understand its meaning easily, in which evokes their psycho-pleasure when using it. The fourth is ideo-pleasure which in the context of products

relates to the aesthetic nature of a product and the values that it embodies. For instance, a product made with recycled material can evoke a user's ideo-pleasure, if she or he agrees with the importance of environmental issues.

Table 1 A comparison of three theories

Types of theories	Appearance pleasure (Evoked by seeing product appearance)	Interactive pleasure* (Evoked by using or interact with product)	Reflective pleasure (Evoked by understanding the meaning of products)
Leong's theory (2003)	The outer "tangible" level	The mid "behavioral" level*	The inner "intangible" level
Norman's Theory (2004)	Visceral level emotion,	Behavioral level emotion*	Reflective level emotion
Jordan's Theory (2000)	Physio-pleasure	Psycho-pleasure*	Socio-pleasure, Ideo-pleasure

Note: Pleasure indicated with '*' are ignored because actual interaction are not the focus of this study.

On the basis of above theories, three levels of product emotions are concluded: (1) Appearance pleasure evoked by perceiving product appearance; (2) Interactive pleasure evoked by using or interacting with product; (3) Reflective pleasure evoked by understanding the meaning of products (see Table 1). The focus of this research mainly is on product appearances and their cultural contents. The behavior level emotion is ignored because of research limitation, which participants can not actual perform physical interaction through images. For this experiment, the present research defines pleasure as "a consumer's positive emotion response elicited by looking at a product's appearance, in which positive emotions are derived from the observing product appearance and the understanding of product contents".

2. Method

In this research, stimuli were selected and used in creating a questionnaire to investigate users' affective responses (raw data) towards products with cultural attributes from 73 participants. Data analysis was used for organizing the raw data into a hierarchical list and, further, for identifying types and characteristics of cultural products. The detailed process is described in the following section.

Stimulus selection: Judgment sampling was adopted for this study. Total 82 product pictures were collected from internet, magazine, books and other sources. Three experts were invited to sort these 82 pictures and 14 product pictures (i.e. two lights, a lamp, three mugs, a bamboo basket, pepper and salt shakers, a juicer, a burner, a thread collector, a scale, a chair and a bench) were selected based on their distinct culture aspects and their common usage in our everyday life. Each stimulus has involved with at least one of three levels of emotions concluded in prior literature review (see Table 1). Total 14 stimuli were used in the questionnaire. Among 14 pictures, 'Desk light', 'Tofu mug', 'Ice block light' and 'Pepper and salt shakers' were indicated to be the top four pleasure samples, according to a high percentage of participants commented that these four stimuli can evoke their pleasure. The numbers of percentage are 83%, 82%, 78% and 72%, while others remained with 68%, 65%, 61%, 61%, 58%, 47%, 46%, 39%, 38% and 33%. In this study, hence, these top four stimuli were selected as distinct samples and had a further analysis to the participants' responses collected from these four. The responses were then used for the development of characteristics and factors later.

Questionnaire : The first page of questionnaire is a guide instruction, where address the purpose of the research and definition of pleasure of this research. Followed with cover page, there is a product picture with color located the top of second page. Aligned the product picture, six question items were used to test participants' pleasure response to the stimulus, product image. The first three question-items were developed in the based of emotional theories concluded in the prior literature review, For instance, "Does this product's appearance (i.e. shape, color, material, etc.) make you feel pleasure? Why? Please describe your reasons"; "Do you think you will feel any pleasure when using this product? Why? Please describe your reasons", and "Does this product make you feel pleasure because it is associated with other objects, events, scenarios or other memories? Please describe these associations with details." After the first three questions, two extra items were asked to understand participants' pleasure and intension to the cultural products. They are "Overall, do you agree that this product can make you feel pleasure? Yes No " and "Will you buy this product when if price is not the consideration? Yes No ".

Subjects : 36 design major students (21 female and 15 male) and 37 professionals (female 25 and 12 male) participated the test. With average age 27.5, total 73 participants (46 female and 27 male) were involved in the test.

Proceeding: Participants were asked to read through guide instruction firstly and, then answered each question intuitively till 14 stimuli were completed.

Data analysis: Data collected from the questionnaire were transcribed into a word processing program in order to analysis and grouping the data. A three-step process was used to analyze the data. The three steps were: 1) data grouping, 2) secondary level labeling, and 3) primary level labeling [28]. Characteristics and factors were then identified.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Characteristics and factors development

Data Grouping: A total of 405 key sentences were identified from the responses and provides the basis of data grouping. Among data, there are 117 key sentences for desk light, 103 for tofu mug, 95 for ice block light and 90 for pepper and salt shakers. Data grouping is a procedure for grouping key sentences having similar content. Key sentences describing the same stimulus and judged to be of similar content were first sorted into the same groups, as shown in Column 3 of Table 2. For instance, participants described Tofu mug using the sentence: "*Tofu mug with square shape demonstrates the beauty of tea cup.*" and Ice block using "*The Ice Block light having a simple shape looks very beautiful.*" Both sentences were categorized into the same group, because their content described the same subject, in this case the beauty of shape. This step involves with repeated and careful reading of the transcribed data in order to develop a clear understanding of the content of each response.

Table 2 Characteristics and factors of pleasurable cultural products

Types	Characteristics (405)	Evidences
Pleasant Appearance (172)	Beautiful shape (45)	TF: Tofu mug with square <u>shape</u> demonstrates the beauty of tea cup. IB: The <u>simple shape</u> of Ice Block looks very beautiful.
	Sensitive material (17)	IB: The <u>material</u> of IceBlock transfers the real ice image by using a transparent effect. DL: The <u>material</u> shows a sense of comfort.
	Delightful color(28)	P&S: The <u>color</u> appears with vivid and glamour. DL: <u>Pure white color</u> delivers a clean-looks- sense.
	Pleasurable image(82)	DL: The object makes participants feel <u>comfortable</u> . TF: Sensing a Tofu delivers a <u>cool-look</u> feeling.
Playful interaction (31)	Interested psychological interaction(6)	IB: IceBlock Looking hot but cold, is very interest. DL: It looks like holding a coffee cup and drinking it.
	Interested physical interaction(16)	DL: It looks to be able to move easily, which is interest. IB: It looks hot, but is not, actually hurt hands when touch it.
	Playfulness (9)	DL: A desk light which, like a candle can be moving around is interest. P&S: It is funny to be looks-like playing a toy.
Cultural content (138)	Historical context(15)	TF: The object reminds me of Chinese food culture. P&S: Watching these objects, I can associate them with ancient Chinese officers in palace.
	Style(42)	P&S: It has Chinese <u>Style</u> . IB: It can be identify with northern Europe characteristics, and <u>style</u> .
	Fantasy scenario(52)	IB: I can picture the ice block in igloo of Eskimos. TF: It is suitable to use for tea time.
	Social interaction(4)	TF: I rather use it to serve friends during friends gathering. P&S It may emphasis a fun and cherish atmosphere.
	Associated images/ meaning(25)	IB: I associated with ice. P&S: I associated with Chinese wedding, and Chinese doll.
Novelty (49)	Unique concept(49)	P&S: It looks different from ordinary objects. IB: A light bulb in an ice block is unique.
Humor/ interest (15)	Interested concept(15)	TF: appearance design is interested. DL: it is interested and is like having a candle light on.

Note: 1. TF indicates Tofu mug; DL for Desk light; P&S for pepper & salt shakers; IB for Ice block light.
2. "(number)" indicates the number of key sentences.

Secondary Level Labeling: Secondary level labeling was the procedure used for labeling the groups that were identified in the previous step. In order to label a group, the key words or meanings that could represent each key sentence were first identified in each sentence. These key words were then categorized or refined. For instance, pepper and salt shakers was described as " *It has a strong Chinese Style.*" and Ice block was described as " *It can be identify with northern Europe characteristics, and style.*" ; these were refined to 'style', the words 'style' was hence used as the secondary level label representing the key words in this group. The labels were then identified as characteristics of pleasure, as shown in Column 2 of Table 2. Other secondary labels chosen for groups of key sentences included the words 'beautiful shape', 'sensitive material', 'delightful color', 'pleasurable image', 'interested psychological interaction', 'interested physical interaction', 'playful', 'historical context', 'style', 'fantasy scenario', 'social interaction', 'associated images/ meaning', 'unique concept', and 'interested concept.'

Primary Level Labeling: Primary level labeling is a procedure for identifying cluster groups according to similarity of secondary level labels, and thus gradually reducing the data to a higher order concept, which is assigned a primary level label. In this case, the primary labels were the five basic types of cultural product with pleasure. For instance, the secondary labels 'historical context,' 'style' and 'fantasy scenario', 'social interaction',

'associated images/meaning' were all associated with cultural contents. Thus, these words were categorized under the primary label 'Cultural Contents,' as shown in Column 1 of Table 2. The grouping process was completed till 405 key sentences were classified.

3.2 Types and characteristics of pleasurable culture products

The final result produced 14 characteristics which can be classified into five types of pleasurable culture products. These five types are 'pleasant appearance', 'playful interaction', 'cultural content', 'novelty', and 'humor/interest'. The 14 characteristics are 'beautiful shape', 'sensitive material', 'delightful color', 'pleasurable image', 'interested psychological interaction', 'interested physical interaction', 'playful', 'historical context', 'style', 'fantasy scenario', 'social interaction', 'associated images/meaning', 'unique concept', and 'interested concept.' Each type was described as follows.

The 'pleasant appearance' includes 'beautiful shape', 'sensitive material', 'delightful color', and 'pleasurable image'. Take color as an example, pepper and salt shakers having a delightful color from Chin Dynasty conveys the beauty of color, particular associated with Chinese empire robe, which make users feel pleasant, commented participants. The 'playful interaction' deals with consumers' pleasure evoked by interacting with products. It contains 'interesting psychological interaction', 'interesting physical interaction', 'playfulness'. For instance, participants commented that the desk light looks like a coffee cup set, which implies the holding of a coffee cup and drinking it. The metaphor somehow evokes participants' pleasant. The 'cultural content' pertains with consumers' pleasure evoked by cultural content. It includes 'historical context', 'style', 'fantasy scenario', 'social interaction', and 'associated images/meaning'. For instance, participants commented that ice block light make them associated it with ice and igloo of Eskimos, which is very interesting and make them feel pleasure. The results illustrates that cultural products courage them to associate them with some particular events or scenarios in the cultural context. These associations in turn make them feel pleasant. Cultural products have a tendency to evoke participants' pleasure.

3.3 The relationship between pleasure and purchase motivation

Gobe (2001) believed that a product with pleasure has a better chance to success in a competitive market [29]. As mentioned, cultural products have a tendency to add emotional value to a product, which increases consumers' purchase motivation respectively. In the survey, the result shows that participants would like to purchase pleasurable product, if price is not the consideration. It also indicates that participants have a higher motivation to purchase a product with pleasure than one without (see Fig. 1). It confirms Creusen, & Snelders' (2002) and Jordan's (1998) research results [30] [2].

In Fig.1, it is noted that both S10 (i.e. Japanese lantern) and S13 (i.e. Wire collector) demonstrated an inconsistent result between pleasure intensity and purchase motivation. The reason reduces the purchase motivation is possibly because S10 contains with an old style while S13 shows a poor usability: both of factors do not fit into participants' expectation or taste perfectly. This can refer to Spiller's theory (2004) that affect is linked to attitudes, expectations and motivations [31]. However, how a consumer's motivation connects with his or her attitude and expectation leads a new issue needed to have a further study.

Fig. 1 Relationship between pleasure and purchase motivation

(1. Y chair, 2 Desk light, 3 Mug with 2D-happy word, 4 Mug with 3D-happy word, 5 Weight scale, 6 Pepper & Salt shakers, 7 Burner, 8 ice block light, 9 Juicer, 10 Japanese lantern, 11 Bench, 12 Tofu mug, 13 Wire collector, 14 Bamboo basket)

3.4 Cultural product requires a cognitive process

Khalid & Helander (2004) stated that users' affection determined by two systems: affective system and cognitive system [21]. Affective system deals with sensory pleasure which is the result of fast human response, while cognitive system deals with the understanding of product contents, which takes a longer route to go through cognitive process. Cultural content takes time to understand its semantic, which associates with human experiences in the evoking of emotions. The user experience and emotion can further engender products to stimulate sales in the market [32]. To do so, products can utilize a commonly-shared culture elements (e.g., from collective memory, stereotypes or metaphors, etc.) which users can perceive its meaning easily and clearly for the enhancement of pleasure value.

In the base of the frequency of key sentences, the result showed that the more participants used key sentences to describe cultural contents, the higher level of emotional response they would possess towards that particular product. This result suggests that designing a unique cultural product should combine with a distinct cultural element, which consumers can decode its content easily and affectively. Regarding to cross-cultural products, it is suggested to have a further study of emotional responses in order to test the difference between two cultures. As we known, consumers' emotion can be evoked through an object, event or agent [33]. This survey concludes five different cultural characteristics: 'historical context', 'style', 'fantasy scenario', 'social interaction', and 'associated images/ meaning'. They can refer to events. Within a variety of cultural characteristics, it may project consumers' experiences through object, event or agent, which may evoke pleasure.

In addition, among five characteristics, novelty and humor/ interest are also mentioned frequently. Consumers mentioned that product with a unique concept attracted their attentions; make them surprise and further pleasant. Similarly, product with an interested idea also makes them smile. In design application, Seva, Duh, & Helander (2007) mentioned that observing people's interaction with products can educate designers on critical user behaviour that can serve as an input to design [32]. Extensively, designers should observe and try to understand how types and characteristics of cultural products affecting a user and selectively embed these characteristics into the designs to increase consumers' pleasures.

3.5 Cultural differences in product design

According to emotional cognitive theory [20], there are two emotion channels: one elicits response immediately, and the other channel required an understanding (cognitive) process, which may take a longer time to decode cultural content and evoke a user's emotion. Moreover, Leur, Drukker, Christiaans, and Rijk (2006) claim that ethnic-cultural variation is reflected in the different products people use and product experience of using environment [34]. It means the results of this study may have a different results when test in different culture users. In other words, can Tofu mugs allow participants from different culture to associate with Chinese Tofu? Do these associations also represent the images of nutrition, delicious and healthy food in Chinese ancient grommet and make participants feel pleasure. According to product semantic theory, Krippendorff (2006) commented that emotions in using an artifact depend on what the artifact means or implies to the user [35]. The responses of motion somehow relies on the result of encoding and decoding process. It implies that consumers' emotions towards cultural products are depended on the individual interpretations of cultural contents of products. Different people with different experience or knowledge may result in different interpretation of the objects and further appear different emotions automatically. In this case, a person having different experience to the Tofu may have different levels of pleasurable response. Similarly, can pepper and salt shaker having a significant cultural color, pattern and historical meaning also result in the same level of pleasure response from different cultural participants. These questions are suggested to have a further cross-cultural study.

4. Acknowledgement

This study is a part of the NSC project which is funded by a grant from National Science Council of Taiwan (Grant no. NSC97-2410-H-182-015). The authors are grateful to C. Y. Hsieh and S. K. Wang for their help in the data arrangement.

5. References

- [1] Marzano, S. (1998). *Thoughts*, Netherlands: V+K Publishing.
- [2] Jordan, P. (1998). 'Human Factors for Pleasure in Product use'. *Applied Ergonomics*, 29(1), 25-33.
- [3] Handa, R. (1999). Against arbitrariness: Architectural signification in the age of globalization. *Design Studies*, 20(4), 363-380.
- [4] Yair, K., Press, M., & Tomes A. (2001). Crafting competitive advantage: Crafts knowledge as a strategic resource. *Design Studies*, 22(4), 377-394.
- [5] Yair, K., Tomes, A., & Press, M. (1999). Design through marking: Crafts knowledge as facilitator to collaborative new product development. *Design Studies*, 20(6), 495-515.
- [6] Lin, R. T. (2007). Transforming Taiwan aboriginal cultural features into modern product design: A case study of a cross- cultural product design model. *International Journal of Design*, 1(2), 45-53.
- [7] Desmet, P. & Overbeeke, K. (2001). 'Designing Products with Added Emotional Value: Research through Design'. *The Design Journal*, 4(1), 32-47.
- [8] Alessi, Alberto, (2000). *The Dream Factory*, Italy: Electa/Alessi.

- [9] Wu, T. Y., Hsu, C. H., & Lin, R. T. (2004). A study of Taiwan aboriginal culture on product design, In J. Redmond, D. Durling, & A. de Bono (Eds.), *Proceedings of Design Research Society International Conference – Futureground*, Melbourne: Monash University.
- [10] Lin, R. T. (2005). Creative learning model for cross cultural products. *Art Appreciation*, 1(12), 52-59.
- [11] Crossley, Lee, (2003). Building emotions in design. *The Design Journal*, 6(3), 35.
- [12] Jordan, P. (2000). *Designing Pleasurable Products*, UK: Tylor and Francis.
- [13] McDonagh-Philp and Lebbon, C. (2000). The emotional domain in product design. *The design journal*, 3, pp.31-43.
- [14] Gotzsch, J. (2002). *Product Charisma*, Common Ground: DRS International Conference, UK.
- [15] Norman, A. D., (2004). *Emotional design*. New York: Basic books.
- [16] Ho, M. C., Lin, C. H., & Liu, Y. C., (1996). Some speculations on developing cultural commodities. *Journal of Design*, 1(1), 1-15.
- [17] Leong, D., & Clark, H. (2003). Culture-based knowledge towards new design thinking and practice- A dialogue. *Design Issues*, 19(3), 48-58.
- [18] Burns, A.D., & Evans, S., (2000). *Insights into Customer Delight*. Chapter 29 in Scrivener, S.A.R., Ball, L.J., Woodcock, A. (Eds), *Collaborative Design*, London: Springer, 195–203.
- [19] Helander, M. G. & Khalid, H. M. (2006). Affective and pleasurable design. In: Salvendy. G. (Ed.). *Handbook on Homan Factors and Ergonomics*. New York: Wiley, 543-572.
- [20] Khalid, M. Halimahtun (2006). Embracing diversity in user needs for affective design, *Applied Ergonomics*, 37, 409-418.
- [21] Khalid, H. M., & Helander, M. G. (2004). A framework for affective customer needs in product design. *Theory Issues Ergon, SCI*. 5 (1), 27-42.
- [22] Oliver, R.L., Rust, R.T., & Varki, S. (1997). Customer Delight: Foundations, Findings and Managerial Insight. *Journal of Retailing*, 73(3), 311-335.
- [23] Crozier, R. (1994). *Manufactured pleasures*, NY: Manchester University Press.
- [24] Van Rompay, T. J. L., Pruyn, A. T. H., & Tieke, P. (2009). Symbolic meaning integration in design and its influence on product and brand evaluation. *International Journal of Design*, 3(2), 19-26.
- [25] De Souza and Dejean (1999). Interculturality and Design: Is Culture a Block or Encouragement to Innovation? *Design Cultures – an International Conference of Design Research*, Sheffield Hallam, UK
- [26] Lahti, Marku (2007). *Objects and furniture design: Alvar Aalto*, Barcelona: Ediciones Poligrafa.
- [27] Tiger, L. (2000). *The Pursuit of Pleasure*. London: Transaction.
- [28] Ulrich T. K. & Eppinger D. S. (2000). *Product design and development*. USA: McGraw-Hill.
- [29] Gobe, M. (2001). *Emotional branding*, NY: Allworth Press.

- [30] Creusen, M. & Snelders, D. (2002). *Product Appearance and Consumer Pleasure*. UK: Taylor and Francis.
- [31] Spillers, Frank (2004). Emotion as a Cognitive Artifact and the Design Implications for Products That are Perceived As Pleasurable, <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.94.4419&rep=rep1&type=pdf> [Accessed 21 May, 2010]
- [32] Seva, R. R. Duh, H. B-L., & Helander, M. G. (2007). The marketing implications of affective product design. *Applied Ergonomics*, 38(6), 723-731.
- [33] Desmet, Peter, (2002). *Designing emotions*, Netherlands: Delft University.
- [34] Leur, K.R. De, Drukker, J.W., Christiaans, H.H.C.M., and Rijk, T.R.A. De (2006). Cultural differences in product design: a study of differences between the South Korean and the Dutch kitchen environment, *J. of Design Research*, 5(1), 4 September, pp. 16-33(18).
- [35] Krippendorff, K. (2006). *The semantics turn: A new foundation for design*. Taylor & Francis/ CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL.